

Nutritional and Health Benefits of Black Plum (*Syzygium Cumini*) for Human Well-Being

Foluso T. Agulanna¹ and Moses O. Ogunlade²

¹Department of Economics and Extension, Economics Section, Cocoa Research Institute of Nigeria, Ibadan.

² Department of Agronomy and Soils, Soil and Plant Nutrition Section, Cocoa Research Institute of Nigeria, Ibadan

Corresponding author: foluagu@yahoo.com +234 8033763258

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Abstract

Black plum (*Syzygium cumini*), also known as jamun, is a tropical fruit tree commonly found in South Asia and parts of Africa, including Nigeria. Traditionally used in herbal medicine, black plum is increasingly recognised as a functional food due to its rich nutritional and phytochemical content. This review explores the nutritional value and health benefits of black plums in enhancing human well-being. The fruit, seeds, leaves, and bark contain key compounds, such as anthocyanins, flavonoids, ellagic acid, and tannins, which contribute to its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, and antimicrobial effects. Nutritionally, black plum is an important source of vitamin C, iron, calcium, and dietary fibre. The paper explores the opportunities of developing black plum into nutraceuticals like supplements, teas, powders, and functional beverages. Evidence from various studies shows its potential for managing a range of health conditions. Nevertheless, despite these benefits, black plum remains underutilised in many regions. The paper, therefore, calls for greater awareness, scientific research, and investment to promote its sustainable use for improved nutrition and health outcomes. By integrating traditional knowledge with modern scientific insights, black plum emerges as a promising natural resource for managing nutrition-related diseases and advancing public health sustainably.

Keywords: Black plum, antioxidant properties, nutritional and health benefits, human wellbeing

INTRODUCTION

Black plum {*Syzygium cumini* (L.) Skeels} also referred to as jamun, jambul or java plum is a tropical evergreen fruit tree belonging to the Myrtaceae family native to South Asia (Ayyanar and Subash, 2012). It is a fast-growing underutilized fruit tree crop that produces oblong, purple-black berries or deep purple fruits with a sweet, astringent taste. It is widely distributed in South and Southeast Asia, and its naturalisation in parts of Africa, including Nigeria, makes it both accessible and culturally significant in traditional medicine systems. *S. cumini* fruits play an important role in traditional medicine and have demonstrated considerable potential in modern scientific investigations. Its therapeutic properties derived from its bioactive compounds, such as alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, and polyphenols, which exhibit diverse pharmacological activities such as anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and anticancer effects.

Traditionally, *S. cumini* has been used in folk medicine for the treatment of ailments including diabetes, digestive disorders, and inflammation. In recent years, with growing global interest

in plant-based nutrition and functional foods, *S. cumini* has attracted scientific attention for its bioactive constituents and health-promoting potential (Ratnayake *et al.*, 2020). Again, increasing attention has been directed toward *S. cumini* because of its dense nutritional composition and phytochemical profile, positioning it as a promising functional food and potential nutraceutical, particularly for preventing and management of non-communicable diseases (Nascimento Silva *et al.*, 2022; Sidana *et al.*, 2017; Ahmad *et al.*, 2017; Gaura *et al.*, 2025). Some studies have reported that *S. cumini* is beneficial for managing diabetes and improving heart health (Bibha *et al.*, 2024, and Jagetia, 2018). The reason is that it is well-adapted to coastal and semi-arid regions where water resources are limited, and conventional crops often fail to thrive (Indira Devi and Jagveer, 2023). The species prefers well-drained soils and moist tropical environments, yet it can tolerate periods of waterlogging (Chen *et al.*, 2021). Consequently, *S. cumini* commonly grows along riverbanks and streamsides, and exhibits drought tolerance once established.

In addition to its ecological resilience, *S. cumini* offers substantial nutritional and medicinal benefits, making it valuable not only for local consumption but also for potential export markets (Jacqueline *et al.*, 2024). Owing to its natural tolerance to climatic stresses, *S. cumini* can play a significant role in addressing the challenges posed by climate change. Its cultivation contributes to food security under shifting environmental conditions while enhancing the nutritional well-being of local communities. The fruits of *S. cumini* are not only important components of local diets but also hold considerable economic value for farmers who can access emerging markets for these nutrient-dense products. Though not indigenous to Nigeria, *S. cumini* has naturalised and is commonly found in home gardens, research stations, and mission compounds. It is primarily found in the southwestern states, where it is occasionally used in local medicine and consumed as a seasonal fruit. Despite its adaptability and numerous benefits, its agricultural and economic potential remains largely underexploited in these regions.

In Nigeria, *S. cumini* is known by various local names: *Orinla* or *Osunfun* in Yoruba; *Dinya India*, *Tsamiya India* or *Dinya baki* in Hausa, and *Uju ocha* or *Osisi jamun* (often referred to as “Indian cherry” among the Igbo, due to its resemblance to the native African cherry). In Southwestern Nigeria, it is commonly found in cities such as Ibadan, Akure, Abeokuta, Osogbo, and Ado-Ekiti, typically in home gardens, forest edges, and traditional compounds.

S. cumini trees thrive in well-drained, deep loamy soils, rich in organic matter, and prefer dry weather during the flowering and fruiting seasons, as excessive moisture can affect flower and fruit set. These trees are drought-tolerant, growing well in regions with low to moderate rainfall, flourishing in tropical and subtropical climates with temperatures ranging from 25°C to 40°C. However, excessive humidity and waterlogged soil can damage the roots, particularly in poorly drained areas.

The species is highly valued for its nutritional and medicinal properties. The fruit is rich in Vitamin C and antioxidants, and is noted for managing diabetes by regulating blood sugar levels (Rizvi *et al.*, 2022). Various parts of the tree, including the fruit, seeds, and bark, are traditionally used to treat digestive disorders, infections, and other ailments (Jagetia, 2017). Its medicinal benefits include its anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and anti-diabetic properties (Abdur *et al.*, 2021). Bioactive compounds like anthocyanins, myricetin, ellagic acid, and isoquercetin contribute to this effect by reducing oxidative stress, improving circulation, and managing chronic inflammation (Parveen *et al.*, 2020).

The seeds contain glycosides such as jambolin and antimellin, which inhibit the conversion of starch into sugar, thereby supporting diabetes management (Biswas and Sen, 2018). The

versatility and medicinal properties of *S. cumini*, combined with its adaptability to diverse environments, make it an important crop in South Asia, with promising applications in food, health, and the pharmaceutical industries.

Botanical Description and Distribution

S. cumini is a fast-growing perennial tropical tree that can attain a height of up to 30 meters. It possesses glossy, oblong leaves and a dense canopy. The plant grows best in wet regions with annual rainfall generally in excess of 1000 mm and may thrive in areas receiving up to 4000 mm, and even as much as 10,000 mm annually. Similarly, it can tolerate drier conditions once established, especially on stony or gravelly soils. Although it thrives better in tropical climates with mean annual temperatures of 25-27°C, *S. cumini* can also grow in sub-tropical areas. Seedlings are frost sensitive, while mature ones have greater frost tolerance (Adak & Singh, 2024).

Despite its ability to flourish in moist lowlands, wet areas, *S. cumini* performs well on elevated, well-drained soils including loams, marls, sands, calcareous soils, and oolitic limestone (Morton, 1963). The tree produces small white flowers, which develop into oblong, deep purple to black fruits. The fruiting season varies by region but typically occurs during the warmer months, depending on the region. Propagation occurs easily from fresh seed, and the species coppices and resprouts easily. *S. cumini* begins fruiting at 8-10 years of age, although budded or grafted trees are more precocious, flowering within 3-4 years. Inflorescences are borne mainly produced mainly from the leaf axils of five to twelve-month-old shoots, though they may also appear terminally or on leafless branches. Pollination is primarily mediated by bees and flies, though wind pollination may also occur. Because the seeds lose viability rapidly after maturation, propagation requires fresh seeds. Dry weather during flowering and fruiting periods generally enriches fruit production.

S. cumini thrives well in moist environments and can tolerate periods of waterlogging (Chen *et al.*, 2021). Consequently, it is commonly found along riverbanks and stream sides, but can also survive, (though less vigorously) on drier sites once established. In its native range, the species is widely cultivated and frequently occurs around homesteads and agricultural lands.

The fruits of *S. cumini* grow in clusters, ranging from a few to as many as 10 to 40. They are round or oblong, often slightly curved, measuring 1.25-5 cm in length, and undergo a distinct colour change from green to light magenta, eventually becoming deep purple or nearly black upon ripening. The skin of the fruit is thin, smooth, glossy, and tightly adherent, which may be purple or white, very juicy, and typically contains a single, oblong seed up to 4 cm long. Occasionally, the fruits may contain two to five tightly compressed seeds within a leathery coat, while some varieties are seedless. Again, the fruits are generally astringent, sometimes to the point of being unpalatable; though the flavour varies from sour to moderately sweet. (Morton, 1963; Flora of China Editorial Committee, 2024).

Pictures of *S. cumini*

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

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Traditional / Ethnobotanical Uses

The fruit (ripe/green) can be eaten fresh, made into juices, preserves; used as a tonic and to improve appetite. The seeds/kernel are used as antidiabetic remedy (powdered seed preparations are common). Bark and leaves are used as astringent and antidiarrheal (bark paste, decoctions) and for wounds; leaves and barks also used in traditional preparations for dysentery and oral ulcers. In Nigeria, for instance, in Kano State botanical gardens, *Syzygium* species among medicinal plants are used locally in gastrointestinal and other folk therapies. The Hausas also record hypoglycaemic/digestive uses in folk medicine. (Ayyanar and Subash-Babu, 2012).

Nutritional Composition of *S. cumini*

The fruit of *S. cumini* is nutritionally dense, containing a wide range of essential vitamins and minerals. It is a rich source of vitamin C, which supports immune function and collagen synthesis, and iron, which is vital for haemoglobin formation and oxygen transport. Moderate levels of calcium, potassium, and magnesium further contribute to cardiovascular and neuromuscular health. The pulp is high in dietary fibre, which aids in digestion and satiety, and its low glycaemic index makes it suitable for diabetic diets. Owing to these attributes, *S. cumini* serves not only as a therapeutic fruit but also as a valuable food resource for addressing micronutrient deficiencies, particularly in low-income populations (Kumar *et al.*, 2022).

The seeds of *S. cumini* are rich in carbohydrates, with starch serving as the key source (Prabakaran *et al.*, 2017). They also contain high dietary fibre and about 8% of protein, while their fat content is low (<1.5g/100g), with a balanced fatty acid profile, of which half is saturated. With a low calorific value (267 kcal/100g), the seeds are nutritionally beneficial in treating obesity due to high fibre and low fat content (Newman, 2022). Moreover, they contain significant amounts of ascorbic acid and essential minerals, including iron, manganese, potassium, chromium, magnesium, zinc, sodium and trace levels of copper and calcium. (Shi *et al.*, 2021).

The nutritional values in *S. cumini* (per 100g edible portion/fresh weight) are moisture (82-86.5%), vitamin C (18 -30mg), iron (0.2–1.6mg), fibre (0.9-1.5g), fat (0.2-0.6g), carbohydrates (14-18g), protein (0.7-0.9g), sodium (25-30mg), potassium (55-60mg), calcium (8-15mg) and phosphorus (15-20mg). (Ghosh *et al.*, 2016; Kumar *et al.*, 2022; Satish *et al.*, 2023; Sridhar & Bhat, 2007; Jaiswal *et al.*, 2018; Swami *et al.*, 2012; Sharma *et al.*, 2020)

Phytochemicals and Bioactive Compounds

Various parts of *S. cumini*, including the roots, stems, leaves, fruits, and seeds, are known to produce a wide array of phytochemicals. *S. cumini* seeds are also rich in diverse phytochemicals, such as sterols, phenolic compounds, saponins, terpenes, and terpenoids with phenolic compounds being the most dominant bioactive group. Leaf extracts also contain various secondary metabolites, such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, and glycosides, as well as essential oils, and are notable for their micronutrient content, including calcium, iron, magnesium, potassium, and zinc (Rezende *et al.*, 2013; Katiyar *et al.*, 2016; Lakshmi and Manasa, 2021).

Table 1: Phytochemical Composition and Health Benefits of *S. cumini*

Phytochemicals	Major Plant Parts	Health Benefits
Flavonoids	Fruit pulp, seed, leaves	Antioxidant, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory
Anthocyanins	Fruit skin, pulp	Antioxidant, anti-aging, cardioprotective

Tannins	Bark, seed coat	Astringent, antidiarrheal, wound healing
Phenolic acids	Bark, seed, pulp	Antimicrobial, antioxidant, anticancer
Ascorbic acid & Carotenoids	Fruit pulp	Immunomodulatory, antioxidant
Alkaloids	Seed, bark	Hypoglycaemic, antidiabetic
Essential oils/ Terpenoids	Leaves, fruit peel	Antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective
Saponins	Seed, bark	Antimicrobial, cholesterol-lowering
Glycosides	Seed, bark	Antioxidant, antidiabetic
Sterols	Leaves, seed	Anti-inflammatory, lipid-lowering

Source: Swami et al., 2012; Rizvi et al., 2022, Jaiswal et al., 2018; Qamar et al., 2022, Sharma et al., 2020; Ayyanar & Subash-Babu, 2012

Health Benefits

S. cumini has long been valued for its bioactive compounds with antiviral, antibacterial, antifungal, and antioxidant properties. These constituents promote wound healing, enhance vitality, and relieve gastrointestinal disorders through their carminative and antacid effects (Katiyar *et al.*, 2016). “Carminative effects” refer to a substance’s ability to relieve or prevent gas formation in the digestive tract, thereby reducing bloating, flatulence, and abdominal discomfort.

Traditionally used to manage diabetes, various parts of the plant, especially the seeds, exhibit anti-diabetic activity, aiding glycaemic control and supporting liver and heart health (Ahmed *et al.*, 2019). The leaves promote oral health, while the bark helps prevent gingivitis and parasitic infections (Ramos and Bandiola, 2017). In all, *S. cumini* serves as an effective, affordable, and safe therapeutic agent.

Apart from the various health benefits identified in the paper already, *S. cumini* is a fruit that is traditionally used in the treatment of respiratory ailments such as colds, coughs, asthma, and bronchitis due to its anti-inflammatory, antibacterial and anti-asthmatic properties (Subramanian *et al.*, 2014). It also contains strong aphrodisiac properties that improve libido, hormone production, and sperm quality while easing anxiety (Kumar *et al.*, 2020). The plant exhibits varied pharmacological effects, including antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, gastroprotective, cardioprotective, antidiarrheal, ant-arthritic, wound-healing, and anticancer functions. However, its hypoglycaemic action may cause such adverse effect as fatigue, indigestion, or respiratory discomfort, especially with excessive use or during pregnancy, though traditional remedies like salt and *Piper nigrum* are used to mitigate these effects many(Jagetia, 2017). Despite extensive documentation of the phytochemical richness and ethnomedicinal applications of *S. cumini*, there are significant research and translational gaps. Most of the available evidence are derived from in vitro assays and animal model studies, controlled human clinical trials validating its therapeutic efficacy are scarce. Another critical limitation is the lack of phytochemical standardization. The concentrations of key bioactives vary widely depending on geographical origin, cultivar, ripening stage and extraction solvent. This variability hinders the establishment of universally accepted standards for *S. cumini* based

nutraceuticals or herbal formulations. For practical translation into nutraceuticals, standardization of the bioactive components and validation of safety profiles are crucial.

Nutraceutical Applications

The many health benefits of *S. cumini* have led to its incorporation in nutraceuticals such as dietary supplements, herbal teas, capsules, powders, fortified beverages and skincare creams. Its fruits are also processed into juices, jams, syrups, dried fruits, and dried products used in health formulations. Owing to its strong anti-hyperglycaemic and antioxidant properties, *S. cumini* is widely used in diabetic care products. These value-added forms enhance accessibility and economic value (Gajera *et al.*, 2023). Ongoing research explores microencapsulation to improve the stability and bioavailability of its bioactive compounds, particularly anthocyanins for pharmaceutical and functional food applications.

CHALLENGES AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The large-scale adoption of *S. cumini* is constrained by inadequate research, poor propagation techniques, limited farmer support and weak supply chains. Post-harvest losses, low processing capacity, and poor consumer awareness further impede market growth. As an underutilized crop, it receives minimal attention in breeding and agronomic studies, particularly in Africa. Realising its economic and nutritional potential requires coordinated investment in research, improved cultivation and processing technologies, and public sensitization through nutrition campaigns and extension programmes (Kumar *et al.*, 2022).

CONCLUSION

The cultivation and utilization of *S. cumini* presents significant opportunities for improving nutritional security and economic development, especially in food-insecure, and environmentally stressed regions. The fruit is rich in vitamins, minerals, proteins, and antioxidants, which help improve dietary diversity, and health. Its resilience to drought, salinity, and poor soils, makes it suitable for marginal areas contributing to food security and livelihood diversification. Beyond its nutritional value, *S. cumini* holds promise for medicinal and commercial applications, creating income opportunities for rural communities. Strategic investment in research, development, and policy support is essential to maximize its potential and ensure sustainable utilisation amid climate change. To fully exploit potentials in *S. cumini*, future research should emphasize human clinical trials, standardization of extract formulations, processing innovation, sustainable cultivation and postharvest handling to maintain phytochemical integrity across the supply chain.

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